

8 Theory On Quantum Fields – Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

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May 11, 2021

Abstract:

By using the coupling constant equation obtained in the new framework 8 Theory as a result of net curvatures, represented on a Lorentz manifold which are prime in their nature, it is possible to extrapolate insights regarding the phenomena of interference in bosonic measurement, which comes to an agreement with the uncertainty principle and the problem of measurement. The new framework allows us to analyze the phenomena in a new and simpler light, by using the first representation of the coupling constant primordial function, i.e. net variation, N_V .

Introduction

We have three main equations:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (3)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (3.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

What are quantum fields in our theory? Since the theory revolves around a varying Lorentz manifold, and the manifold is all we aspire to describe. A quantum field would be described as ripples and interference **on a manifold**. Fermions or spinor fields would be describes as interferences on the manifold, arbitrary amount of curving, a certain hyperbole if you will. Boson fields would be than waves propagating across the entire manifold.

We do not have any data to describe the time or direction of propagation of bosons from the interferences on a stationary manifold, which are fermions. That is with complete agreement with the physics of the 20-th century. The boson fields will propagate across and scatter the entire manifold. Suppose we would like to detect the location of a boson after it was emitted from a fermion.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

To do such thing we need to locate the boson, we scatter the area by a ray of additional Photons, let's assume is a small number:

$$2N \text{ Bosons} \rightarrow N = 500$$

$$1000 * \frac{1}{2} = 500$$

After the scattering by 1000 photons, the system is completely different we have:

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + 500 = \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + 500.5$$

If we were able to locate the location of the particle, we added to it, an amount of photon pressure and its momenta now varied. A single boson was effected by the additional Cluster of bosons we directed at it. That is in agreement with the Heisenberg principle of Uncertainty. The framework also does not have any details on the location of the electron.

In our framework, the electron is the $\frac{1}{2}$ marked in green (only for this element in the series). We have no data with regard to its location, its orbital around the nucleus, its momenta or its motion. Since our framework is mathematical, we do not have any way to extract data with regard to those features of nature. On the other hand, it comes to certain Agreement with modern physics, and the nature of the electron. In our framework is invariant (3) is blending in the cluster larger variation cluster. We do not know where it is, or when it was inserted. That is intersecting with not knowing when an electron will be propagated from a quark.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)